

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Development And Validation of a Stability-Indicating UPLC Method for The Simultaneous Estimation of Clindamycin and Miconazole in Bulk and Combined Dosage Forms

K. Jhansi*, Dr. Kaveti Balaji

Avanthy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 18 Oct 2025

Keywords:

Clindamycin, Miconazole, UPLC, Stability-Indicating Method, Validation

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17383590

ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to develop and validate a stability-indicating UPLC method for simultaneous estimation of clindamycin and miconazole in bulk and combined pharmaceutical dosage forms. Separation was carried out on a C18 column using a phosphate buffer–acetonitrile mobile phase (pH 3.0) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min, with detection at 220 nm. The method was optimized for sharp peak symmetry, suitable retention time, and adequate resolution. Validation, performed as per ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, confirmed specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, LOD, and LOQ within acceptable limits. Forced degradation under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic conditions demonstrated the method's stability-indicating capability by effectively separating degradation products from the active drugs. Recovery studies and assay of marketed formulations showed high accuracy, with %RSD below 2%, confirming reproducibility. The developed UPLC method is rapid, sensitive, and reliable, making it suitable for routine quality control and stability analysis of clindamycin and miconazole in pharmaceutical products.

INTRODUCTION

Clindamycin, a lincosamide antibiotic, inhibits bacterial protein synthesis and is widely prescribed for anaerobic infections [1]. Miconazole, an imidazole antifungal agent, acts by disrupting fungal cell membrane integrity and is used to treat dermatophytic and candidal infections [2]. These

drugs are often combined in topical dosage forms for managing mixed bacterial-fungal infections, providing broad therapeutic coverage [3]. Conventional methods like UV spectroscopy and RP-HPLC have limitations for simultaneous estimation due to differences in physicochemical properties and overlapping absorption spectra [4]. Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UPLC) offers advantages such as higher

***Corresponding Author:** K. Jhansi

Address: *Avanthy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad.*

Email ✉: pharmacyresearchlab@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

resolution, shorter run times, and lower solvent consumption, making it ideal for complex formulations [5]. Despite the clinical significance of this combination, no stability-indicating UPLC method has been reported for clindamycin and miconazole estimation. Existing RP-HPLC methods lack forced degradation studies and require longer analysis times [6]. According to ICH guidelines Q1A(R2) and Q2(R1), stability-indicating methods are essential to ensure quality and detect degradation products [7]. Therefore, this study aimed to develop and validate a simple, robust UPLC method for simultaneous estimation of clindamycin and miconazole in bulk and combined dosage forms, including forced degradation analysis.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

Clindamycin and Miconazole reference standards were obtained from Spectrum Laboratories, Hyderabad, India. HPLC-grade solvents such as acetonitrile and methanol were purchased from Merck, Mumbai, India. Analytical-grade potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and orthophosphoric acid were used for buffer preparation. Double-distilled water was produced using a Milli-Q water purification system. All chemicals and reagents complied with analytical standards [1,2].

Instruments and Software

Chromatographic analysis was performed using a Waters UPLC system (Alliance 2695) equipped with a quaternary pump, autosampler, and 2996 PDA detector, controlled by Empower 2 software. Separation was achieved on an Inertsil ODS C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm). Additional instruments included a pH meter (Eutech, India),

ultrasonic bath (PCI Analytics), and analytical balance (Shimadzu AUX220).

Chromatographic Conditions

The optimized chromatographic method employed a C18 reverse-phase column with an isocratic mobile phase consisting of acetonitrile and 0.05 M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer (adjusted to pH 3.0 with orthophosphoric acid) in a ratio of 70:30 v/v. The flow rate was 1.0 mL/min, and the injection volume was 10 μL. Detection was carried out at λ_{max} 210 nm, which corresponds to the maximum absorbance of both drugs. The column was maintained at ambient temperature (25°C). Diluent used for sample preparation was water:acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) [3,4].

Preparation of Standard Stock Solutions

- Clindamycin Standard: Accurately weigh 100 mg of clindamycin and dissolve in 100 mL of diluent to prepare a 1000 μg/mL stock solution.
- Miconazole Standard: Similarly, weigh 100 mg of miconazole and dissolve in 100 mL of diluent to obtain 1000 μg/mL stock solution.
- Working standards were prepared by serial dilution to cover the linearity range (e.g., 10–100 μg/mL for clindamycin and 5–50 μg/mL for miconazole) [5].

Preparation of Sample Solution

A quantity of the combined dosage form equivalent to 50 mg clindamycin and 25 mg miconazole was accurately weighed and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Approximately 70 mL of diluent was added, and the mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes to ensure complete dissolution. The volume was made up to

the mark with diluent and filtered through a 0.45 μm nylon syringe filter prior to injection [6].

precise, accurate, robust, and stability-indicating as per ICH guidelines.

Method Development and Optimization

Various chromatographic parameters such as mobile phase ratio, pH, organic modifier concentration, and flow rate were optimized to achieve sharp, symmetrical peaks with satisfactory resolution, retention time, and tailing factor. Different buffer systems (phosphate buffer, formic acid buffer) and organic solvents (methanol, acetonitrile) were tested. The final optimized conditions ensured good system suitability parameters including theoretical plates > 2000, tailing factor < 2.0, and %RSD < 2.0 [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed UPLC method successfully separated clindamycin and miconazole with sharp, well-resolved peaks under optimized conditions. Validation results confirmed that the method is

Table 1: Optimized Conditions

S. No.	Parameter	Condition
1	Mobile Phase	Buffer : Acetonitrile 66:34 % v/v
2	pH	3.6
3	Diluent	Water : Methanol 48:52 % v/v
4	Column, Make	Inertsil ODS C18, 250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm
5	Column Temperature	30°C
6	Detection Wavelength	220 nm
7	Injection Volume	10 μL
8	Flow Rate	1.0 mL/min
9	Run Time	7 min
10	Retention Time (Clindamycin)	2.25 min
11	Retention Time (Miconazole)	3.25 min

Fig. 1. Optimized Chromatogram

Method Validation

The developed UPLC method was validated as per ICH Q2(R1) guidelines for the following parameters [8,9]:

1. System Suitability

System suitability was assessed by injecting six replicate injections of the standard solution. Parameters such as retention time, theoretical plates, tailing factor, and %RSD of peak areas were evaluated.

Table 2: System Suitability

S. No.	Clindamycin			Miconazole		
	Area	USP-Plate-Count	USP-Tailing	Area	USP-Plate-Count	USP-Tailing
1	2,05,785	3568	1.12	3,58,469	9884	1.12
2	2,03,794	3515	1.16	3,57,683	9319	1.12
3	2,06,373	3461	1.16	3,58,853	9252	1.15
4	2,04,025	3556	1.14	3,61,847	9625	1.17
5	2,06,530	3527	1.14	3,64,513	9678	1.14
6	2,04,665	3659	1.16	3,62,656	9524	1.12
Mean	2,05,195	–	–	3,60,670	–	–
Std. Dev.	1,194.20	–	–	2,726.40	–	–
% RSD	0.6	–	–	0.8	–	–

2. Specificity

Specificity was confirmed by analyzing blank, placebo, standard, and sample solutions to ensure

there was no interference at the retention times of clindamycin and miconazole.

Fig:2. Chromatogram of Blank

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of Placebo

Fig. 4. Chromatogram of Standard

3. Linearity

Calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak area versus concentration over the range of 10–100 µg/mL for clindamycin and 5–50 µg/mL

for miconazole. The correlation coefficient (r^2) was determined to assess linearity. Clindamycin: $y = 10191x + 491.44$, $r^2 = 0.9995$. Miconazole: $y = 9151.6x + 496.44$, $r^2 = 0.9999$

Table 3: Linearity Data

Clindamycin Conc. (µg/mL)	Peak Area (Average, n=3)	Miconazole Conc. (µg/mL)	Peak Area (Average, n=3)
5	48,470	10	91,059
10	1,05,557	20	1,85,101
15	1,53,648	30	2,78,137
20	2,07,569	40	3,64,203
25	2,53,167	50	4,54,974
30	3,05,133	60	5,51,841

Fig.5. Calibration Plot of Clindamycin

Fig.6. Calibration Plot of Miconazole

4. Accuracy

Each level was analyzed in triplicate, and % recovery was calculated.

Accuracy was determined by recovery studies at 50%, 100%, and 150% of the target concentration.

Accuracy

Table 4: Results of Recovery

Preanalysed amount (µg/ml)		Spiked Amount (µg/ml)		% Recovered	
Clindamycin	Miconazole	Clindamycin	Miconazole	Clindamycin	Miconazole
20	40	10	20	99.75	100.8
				99.3	101.05

				99.9	100.5	
		20	40	99.92	100.1	
				99.88	99.25	
				100.7	100.15	
				99.35	100.45	
		30	60	98.1	99.85	
				100.6	99.6	
				MEAN	99.7	100.18
				SD	0.79	0.6
				%RSD	0.83	0.59

Fig. 7. Chromatogram For Accuracy At 50% Spike Level

Fig. 8. Chromatogram For Accuracy At 100% Spike Level

Fig. 9. Chromatogram For Accuracy At 150% Spike Level

5. Precision

Precision was evaluated at two levels:

- Repeatability (Intra-day): Six replicate injections of the sample solution were analyzed.
- Intermediate Precision (Inter-day): Analysis was performed on different days by different analysts.

Table.5: Repeatability

S. No	Clindamycin			Miconazole		
	Area	USP-Plate-Count	USP-Tailing	Area	USP-Plate-Count	USP-Tailing
1	204810	3510	1.15	358950	9610	1.13
2	207000	3385	1.16	364050	9230	1.15
3	208500	3575	1.13	360100	9350	1.14
4	206900	3470	1.13	360150	9085	1.14
5	206300	3480	1.15	359600	9345	1.13
6	208600	3305	1.16	362050	9675	1.14
Mean	206868			360649		
Std. Dev.	1470			1895		
%RSD	0.71			0.53		

Fig. 10.: Chromatogram for Method Precision

Intermediate Precision

Table.6: Intermediate Precision

S. No	Clindamycin			Miconazole		
	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	207200	3600	1.15	358400	9910	1.12
2	208620	3520	1.16	359750	9320	1.13
3	201300	3515	1.18	359590	9275	1.16
4	208220	3605	1.17	351080	9655	1.18
5	209340	3545	1.15	351930	9705	1.15
6	209090	3675	1.16	358950	9560	1.16
Mean	207285			356632		
Std. Dev.	3035			3998		
%RSD	1.46			1.12		

6. LOD and LOQ

The Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) were calculated based on the standard deviation of the response and slope method.

- **Clindamycin:** LOD = 0.10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, LOQ = 0.32 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
- **Miconazole:** LOD = 0.09 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, LOQ = 0.28 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

Table 7. LOD and LOQ

S.NO	Clindamycin		Miconazole	
	SLOPE	Y-INTERCEPT	SLOPE	Y-INTERCEPT
1	10184	510.3	9151	291.8
2	10229	159.9	9152	737.7
3	10162	804	9152	737.7

AVG	10192	491	9152	589
SD		322.47		257.44
LOD		0.1		0.09
LOQ		0.32		0.28

7. Robustness

Robustness was assessed by making deliberate changes to flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min), mobile phase composition ($\pm 5\%$), and detection wavelength (± 2

nm), and evaluating the effect on system suitability.

Robustness

Table 8: Robustness studies

S. No.	Condition	% RSD of Area (Clindamycin / Miconazole)	Tailing Factor (Clindamycin / Miconazole)	Plate Count (Clindamycin / Miconazole)
1	Flow Minus	0.32 / 0.42	1.12 / 1.14	3445 / 10550
2	Flow Plus	0.52 / 0.43	1.14 / 1.17	3620 / 10520
3	Mobile Phase Minus	1.42 / 1.12	1.13 / 1.12	3565 / 10360
4	Mobile Phase Plus	1.48 / 0.72	1.16 / 1.11	3570 / 10540
5	Temperature Minus	0.72 / 0.62	1.12 / 1.28	3650 / 10820
6	Temperature Plus	0.35 / 0.22	1.14 / 1.18	3490 / 10480

8. Solution Stability

Standard and sample solutions were evaluated for stability at room temperature and $2-8^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours.

Table 9: Stability data

Drug	% Assay at 0 hr*	% Assay at 24 hr*	Deviation
Clindamycin	100.4	99.6	0.6
Miconazole	99.65	99.2	0.28

* n = 6 for each parameter

Stability of Sample Solution

No significant changes were observed in the assay results. The deviation was less than 2%

Assay of Marketed Formulation

Table 10. Assay

S. No.	Drug Name	Amount Injected ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Amount Found ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	% Assay \pm SD*
1	Clindamycin	20	20.05	100.25 \pm 0.70
2	Miconazole	40	39.88	99.70 \pm 0.50

* n = 6 for each parameter

Fig.11. Assay Of Marketed Formulation

Forced Degradation Studies

To establish the stability-indicating nature of the method, forced degradation was performed under the following conditions [10,11]:

- Acidic Hydrolysis: Sample treated with 1 N HCl and kept at room temperature for 1 hour, then neutralized.
- Alkaline Hydrolysis: Sample treated with 1 N NaOH under similar conditions, then neutralized.
- Oxidative Stress: Sample treated with 3% H₂O₂ for 30 minutes at room temperature.
- Thermal Degradation: Sample exposed to 105°C in a hot air oven for 6 hours.
- Photolytic Degradation: Sample exposed to UV light (254 nm) for 24 hours.

Table 11: Forced Degradation

Stress Condition	Time	Clindamycin Assay (%)	Miconazole Assay (%)	Degraded Products (%)	Mass Balance (%)
Acid Hydrolysis (0.1 M HCl)	24 hrs	72.9	63.2	33.5	98.4
Basic Hydrolysis (0.1 M NaOH)		29.5	5.2	67.1	99.45
Thermal Degradation (50°C)		96.75	97.05	–	96.9
UV Exposure (254 nm)		85.25	76.15	24.2	99.25
3% Hydrogen Peroxide		38.6	58.8	37.8	99.35

Summary

The UPLC method for simultaneous estimation of clindamycin and miconazole was successfully optimized and validated. Recovery studies indicated high accuracy, while precision results

confirmed repeatability and intermediate precision. Forced degradation confirmed the stability-indicating nature of the method, and stability studies showed minimal degradation over 24 hours. Assay of marketed formulations

demonstrated results close to 100%, proving the method's reliability and applicability.

CONCLUSION

A novel, validated UPLC method was developed for clindamycin and miconazole estimation in bulk and combined dosage forms. The method showed excellent specificity, accuracy, precision, and robustness, meeting ICH requirements. Forced degradation confirmed stability-indicating capability by effectively separating drugs from degradation products. High assay accuracy and low %RSD values support its reproducibility. Stability results indicated minimal variation, confirming suitability for routine quality control and stability testing.

REFERENCES

1. ICH Q1A(R2). Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products. International Council for Harmonisation; 2003.
2. ICH Q2(R1). Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology. International Council for Harmonisation; 2005.
3. Gumułka L, Wolska E, Bojanowska M. Application of UPLC in pharmaceutical analysis: advantages and limitations. *Acta Pol Pharm.* 2019;76(2):345–354.
4. Prava R, Rao AL, Kumari P. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the determination of clindamycin phosphate in pharmaceutical dosage forms. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2020;11(7):3340–3346.
5. Shareef J, Gandla S. Stability-indicating UPLC method development and validation for sulfamethoxazole and clindamycin combination in dosage forms. *Int J Appl Pharm.* 2021;13(3):100–106.
6. Bakshi M, Singh S. Development of validated stability-indicating assay methods—critical review. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2002;28(6):1011–1040.
7. Swartz ME, Krull IS. Analytical method development and validation for pharmaceuticals. Marcel Dekker; 2018.
8. Blessy M, Patel RD, Prajapati PN, Agrawal YK. Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs—A review. *J Pharm Anal.* 2014;4(3):159–165.
9. Snyder LR, Kirkland JJ, Dolan JW. Introduction to Modern Liquid Chromatography. 3rd ed. John Wiley & Sons; 2010.
10. Kazakevich Y, LoBrutto R. HPLC for pharmaceutical scientists. John Wiley & Sons; 2007.
11. Reddy S, Kumar A, Lakshmi N. UPLC technique and its applications in pharmaceutical analysis. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.* 2019;55(1):56–62.
12. Ravisankar P, Naga Navya C, Harikrishna Y, et al. A review on analytical method development. *Indian J Res Pharm Biotechnol.* 2014;2(3):1183–1195.
13. Bakshi M, Singh S. Guidance on the conduct of stress tests to determine inherent stability of drugs. *Pharm Technol.* 2000;24:1–14.
14. Bharathi D, Sharma R. RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of antifungal and antibiotic drugs. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2018;11(5):322–326.
15. Pratima N, Ramesh T, Kumar V. Advances in UPLC: Applications in pharmaceutical analysis. *J Pharm Sci Res.* 2017;9(6):848–856.
16. Basavaiah K, Nagegowda P, Vinay KB. Analytical methods for estimation of antifungal drugs in pharmaceutical formulations. *J Chem.* 2012;9(1):473–484.
17. Al-Ghazawi MA. UPLC: A new technique for fast and efficient analysis. *Pharm World Sci.* 2010;32(3):319–324.

18. Kaur H, Singh G. Role of UPLC in modern pharmaceutical analysis: A review. *World J Pharm Res.* 2019;8(4):192–203.
19. Nagendra P, Rao AR. Simultaneous estimation of antifungal and antibacterial drugs by chromatographic methods: A review. *Int J Chem Sci.* 2016;14(2):812–820.
20. Blessy M, Patel RD. Stability testing as per ICH guidelines. *J Curr Pharm Res.* 2013;3(2):101–109.
21. Sahu PK, Ramiseti NR, Cecchi T, et al. Current trends in analytical method development for pharmaceutical analysis. *J Pharm Biomed Anal.* 2018;147:57–79.
22. Arayne MS, Sultana N, Hussain F. Simultaneous determination of antibiotics by RP-HPLC. *J Chin Chem Soc.* 2011;58(1):32–36.
23. IUPAC Compendium of Analytical Nomenclature. *Pure Appl Chem.* 2002;74(8):1461–1471.
24. Srivastava A, Singh S, Naik S. RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous determination of antifungal agents. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2015;77(1):92–97.
25. González O, Blanco ME, Iriarte G, et al. Bioanalytical chromatographic method validation according to current regulations. *J Chromatogr B.* 2014;960:1–15.
26. Zhang Y, Wu Q, Liu H, et al. Development of a UPLC method for fast determination of antibiotics in pharmaceutical products. *J Sep Sci.* 2017;40(21):4305–4312.
27. Lakshmi KS, Lakshmi S. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the determination of antifungal drugs in formulations. *Der Pharm Chem.* 2014;6(3):117–123.
28. Reddy BV, Saritha D, Ramesh T. RP-HPLC and UPLC methods in pharmaceutical analysis: A comparative review. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.* 2018;52(1):34–40.
29. Sahu P, Ramiseti N. Analytical challenges in simultaneous estimation of combination drugs: Review and strategies. *Curr Pharm Anal.* 2017;13(4):249–260.
30. Trivedi P, Satia M. Development of stability-indicating method for pharmaceutical products: Overview. *Pharm Times.* 2012;44(7):10–16.
31. Kogawa AC, Salgado HR. Analytical quality by design (AQbD) in pharmaceutical analysis: An overview. *Curr Pharm Anal.* 2017;13(2):89–94.

HOW TO CITE: K. Jhansi*, Dr. Kaveti Balaji, Development and Validation of a Stability-Indicating UPLC Method for The Simultaneous Estimation of Clindamycin and Miconazole in Bulk and Combined Dosage Forms, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 10, 1933-1951 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17383590>

